

Statistical Analysis, Design of Experiments, Random Error and Bias

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Abstract: This article refers to the measurement error and selection of appropriate statistical designs for data collection and analysis. The dichotomy persisted in terms of methods of quantification, value or weight assignment respectively in scientific and analytical researches. Most of the scientific researches follow a standardized basis of measurement whereas, in social sciences biases could occur due to adopting non standardized quantification methods especially in cases of assigning values or weights to different parameters or variables. In addition, many researchers and social scientists also fail in selecting appropriate statistical designs from the start. They follow certain examples provided in text books of statistics. It would be noted that there are all the possibilities that those data may be pseudo, manufactured, polished, or crafted. Therefore, blind reliance over such examples without application of mind would give biased results which cannot be assignable at any later stage after the data collection.

Key words: Data Quantification; Measurement Bias; Selection Bias; Statistical Analysis.

Introduction:

Prior to planning a research we must consider two sources of error when planning research such as random error and bias. Bias occurs when the results of a study are systematically different from 'truth'. Bias should be distinguished from random error, in that random error cannot be associated with a particular cause and tends to 'average out' in repeated sampling. Bias, on the other hand, would repeat the same direction of error in repeated sampling with the same design. Bias results from faulty design. There may be many reasons for bias, and care has to be taken to minimize bias when designing the study, since it is often difficult to separate the true effects from bias. Simply increasing the sample size, on the other hand, can minimize the effect of random error.

The knowledge about data, its type such as discrete or continuous is crucial to select a design of experiment and analysis of data. The concepts of data quantifications largely influence the parametric or non-parametric tests we select. We should not forget that there are appropriate analytical methods for different data types and parametric and non-parametric experiments. Several non-parametric experiments corresponds to certain parametric experiments. If the data is not uniformly distributable and parameters are not fixed at initial stage we would suffer from irreversible bias that would be not assignable.

As a reviewer of a journal I used to come across several such papers and articles where statistical analysis is used without considering data type. Statistics is an applied area of mathematics that can provide magical results if applied appropriately. Statistics is an old science and it could be dated back to thousand years according to ancient Indian texts. The mathematics in ancient India was not complete without statics. The measurement of respective distance between the planets of the solar system was never solely based upon mathematics alone as it extensively used statics. The art and science of statistics and mathematics from ancient India was spread in Europe via Arabs, Greeks, and Romans.

There is a difference between a science, puzzle, and magic. Statistics is not puzzle or magic, it is a full independent science contributed by modern statisticians in Europe, America, and other countries such as Japan and Germany.

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In modern times statistics required to taught to students and scholars comprehensively. Attending various research methodology courses I have come to realize that statistics is not taught in comprehensive and details manner. It has resulted in lack of expertise among students and scholars. There are some software such as SPSS, R, EXCEL, and Others however, that would not be sufficient until and unless we would graduate over the basic concepts of data quantification, and analysis. Software used to save time of lengthy calculations however we must also remember all formulas and equations however it would not be possible to remember different tables such as z, t, f, r, Anova,

and Chi square tables. In any case such tables may be used as ready references.

The use statistics, control charts have become so important in modern engineering, technology, and industrial fields. Likewise it is also used in biomedical, weather forecasting, environmental, and chemical sciences. In academic filed some three decades back it was thought proper to award Ph.D. to those students who used to successfully conduct at least one test. However, with improvement in tools and techniques students must be prepared to conduct many such tests on their own. Students must be prepared to work independently on various tests and deigns.

Sampling error

Such errors occur mainly because failure of the identified population and selection of sample from them that could be both adequate and representative. Once the population has been identified and the size of the sample determined, we also need to decide how we are going to choose the sample from the population. The size of the sample will also depend on this choice and therefore, the issue of sample size may have to be revisited.

The sampling error may be classified as followings:-

Error in Simple random sample

This is the most common error because of the fact that it being one among the simplest sampling methods. In this method, the subjects are chosen from the population with equal probability of selection.

The simple random sample has the advantages that it is easy to administer, is representative of the population in the long run, and the analysis of data using such a sampling scheme is straightforward. However, the main error associated with this method has been that of the sample being not truly representative of the population, especially if the sample size is small. In this case even the large sample size could not be truly representative.

Error in Stratified sampling

This types of errors could occur because the unequal distributions of population divided in different strata. If the population in all the stratum under the study are equally distributed then we can chose appropriate number of samples from each strata. Therefore it required to stratify the strata considering homogenous and heterogeneous characters. In one strata homogenous population may be stratified. .

Errors in Cluster sampling

In many administrative surveys, studies are done on large populations which may be geographically quite dispersed. To obtain the required number of subjects for the study by a simple random sample method will require large costs and will be inconvenient. In such cases, error happen mainly due to the fact that clusters identified may have data variations as data within

the cluster and between the clusters may differ. For example if we have to form a cluster after identifying high income group people or households from a town or colony and due to error several low or middle income group people may also get included in the cluster. Even there may be difference in attributes of different clusters that may produce errors.

Error in Multi-stage sampling

Many studies, especially large nationwide surveys, usually incorporate different sampling methods for different groups, and are usually done in several stages. If there would be lack of cohesion in properly identifying the samples or cohorts such error may happen.

. Types of bias

Types of biases could be many different scholars have identified and categorized biases in more than of 100 types. Some have categorized as high as 19 and 65 biases occurring in a research. Only those biases could be corrected by the appropriate research design pre tested and verified form different parameters. As such biases could not be corrected after onset of the research process and data collection. We must also workout in preventing ourselves in framing, illogical hypothesis, and creating a situation where there would be a lack of relationship between research objectives, questions, hypothesis, and methods. After all, if we could not meet the objectives then there is no need of such a lengthy research process. Ultimately, the quantum and types of biases largely depended upon the type of the studies.

Selection bias

Selection bias is a distortion of the estimate of effect resulting from the manner in which the study population is selected. This is probably the most common type of bias, and occurs in observational, as well as analytical studies including experiments.

Prevalence-incidence bias

This type of bias can be introduced into a case-control study as a result of selective survival among the prevalent cases. In selecting cases, we are having a late look at the disease; if the exposure occurred years before, mild cases that improved, or severe cases that died would have been missed and not counted among the cases. This bias is not often a problem in cohort studies and experiments, but is quite common in case-control studies.

c. Non-response bias

This type of bias is due to refusals to participate in a study. The individuals concerned are likely to be different from individuals who do participate. Non-respondents must be compared with respondents with regard to key exposure and outcome variables in order to ascertain the relative degree of non-response bias. Non-response bias is common in all types of studies, but is more

serious in observational studies. In particular, sample surveys are more prone to this type of bias. If the non-response is similar in the exposure and non-exposure groups (or cases and controls), this may not be a serious problem. Sufficient information about related variables should be included in data collection instruments in order that we can verify the effect of non-response bias on the results. Maximizing the response rate in surveys is one way to minimize this type of bias. In randomized controlled trials, it is possible to collect information on related factors that might shed light on the seriousness of the problem by prospectively collecting information and comparing it.

Ascertainment or information bias

Information bias is a distortion in the estimate of effect due to measurement error or misclassification of subjects according to one or more variables.

Effect of selection and ascertainment bias on odds ratios

The biases mentioned in the previous section can alter the odds ratio, and thus potentially lead to an invalid conclusion. The non-response bias can influence both case-control and cohort studies, as well as experiments, and can occur in either direction. Selection biases are the most difficult to avoid. The prevalence-incidence bias cannot be prevented in a case control study, but is at least partially measurable. Non-response bias can be both prevented and measured. Of the ascertainment biases, the diagnostic bias will inflate the odds ratio in both case-control and cohort studies.

Selection biases make it impossible to generalize the results, while the measurement biases influence the validity of the study conclusions. Since biases are difficult to control in most cases, care should be taken to prevent their occurrence by the choice of appropriate design, development of strict protocols and adherence to these protocols. In the worst case, when these biases cannot be prevented, the potential biases should at least be measured, and possible statistical adjustments of results considered.

Confounding

Confounding is a special type of bias. Two variables may give the impression that they are related to each other. However, in fact there is no relationship between the two variables.

Methods for minimizing the biases

1. Cases should be limited to incident cases, and should be chosen as homogeneous entities or as random samples of all cases.
2. Definitions, ascertainment and exclusions must always be made explicit, and this should be done in advance.
3. At least two control groups should be chosen:

4. Analysis should be complete. All known potential confounders, if not already considered in the matching process, should be the subject of analysis by stratification or multivariate techniques.

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